

This Glossary constitutes an official deliverable of Work Package 2: Upskilling of academic communities towards socio-academic empowerment, prepared within the framework of the Erasmus+ KA2 project EGAL-I: Fostering socio-academic inclusion, innovation and justice for refugee students.

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Section	Term	Associated terms (if applicable)	Working definition	Source
1. Target groups, groups involved & institutions				
1.1.	Refugee	<i>Asylum seeker/ Internally Displaced Persons / Exiled person / Stateless person / Person with temporary or subsidiary protection / Paperless person / Undocumented person / migrant</i>	A refugee is any person: "Who has been considered a refugee under the Agreements of 12 May 1926 and 30 June 1928, or under the Conventions of 28 October 1933 and 10 February 1938 and the Protocol of 14 September 1939 or under the Constitution of the International Organization for Refugees [...]. Or, Who, as a result of events occurring before 1 January 1951 and owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and who is unable or, because of this fear, does not want to avail itself of the protection of this country; or who, if he or she does not have a nationality and is outside the country in which he or she was habitually resident as a result of such events, is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to return to it [...]" Within the EGAL-I framework, the term "refugee" is used as a hyponym that encompasses other categories, such as asylum seekers, exiled individuals, and stateless individuals.	United Nations. (1951, July 28). Convention relating to the status of refugees. https://www.unhcr.org/3b66c2aa10
1.2.	Refugee student (already enrolled in a study programme in the country of arrival)	<i>Refugee interested in studying (who in their countries of origin already has secondary study diploma or higher education, with ability to prove it or lost this proof) / Exiled student</i>	In the EU migration context, "a third-country national accepted by an establishment of higher education and admitted to the territory of an EU Member State to pursue as their main activity a full-time course of study leading to a higher education qualification recognised by the EU Member State, including diplomas, certificates or doctoral degrees in a higher education institution, which may cover a preparatory course prior to such education, in accordance with national law, or compulsory training." (Asylum and Migration Glossary, 04/25). In the EGAL-I project, we include refugees who are interested in studying in the category of "refugee student." This is defined as a person who wishes to pursue a higher education (HE) qualification in the host country but first needs to learn the language of that country or needs to overcome other barriers before they are able to start their studies. For example they must take language courses to improve their socio-linguistic and academic language skills in order to gain access to HE programmes taught in the national language.	European Migration Network. (2025, April). Asylum and migration glossary (Version 10.0). European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/assets/home/ern-glossary/glossary.html?letters=&classification=3.3&items=0&detail=student
1.3.	Higher education institutions (HEIs)		Organizations such as universities, colleges and other postsecondary schools that provide education beyond secondary level, usually leading to degrees, diplomas or other recognized qualifications.	Britannica Editors. (2026, January 16). Higher education. In Encyclopedia Britannica. https://www.britannica.com/topic/higher-education
1.4.	Civil society actors and groups		Civil society refers to all forms of social action carried out by individuals or groups who are neither connected to nor managed by state authorities. It ranges from informal local initiatives which start informally and without any particular status (e.g. social media groups) to highly formal and structured non governmental organisations which operate internationally. A civil society organisation is an organisational structure whose members serve the general interest through a democratic process and which plays the role of mediator between public authorities and citizens. Article 15 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union recognises civil society's role in the good governance of the European Union (EU). Article 11 of the Treaty on European Union stresses the need for the EU to have an open, transparent and regular dialogue with civil society organisations, for example when preparing proposals for EU laws. Examples of such organisations include: social partners (trades unions and employers' groups); non-governmental organisations (e.g. for environmental and consumer protection); grassroots organisations (e.g. youth and family groupings).	EUR-Lex. (n.d.) Civil society organisation, In Access to European Union Law. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/civil-society-organisation.html
2. Concepts of Integration & inclusion				
2.1	Integration		Integration is a multidimensional and context-specific process through which individuals or groups gain access to key domains of society, develop meaningful social relationships, and achieve participation, security, and a sense of belonging within the wider social, economic, and institutional structures of a host society - without abandoning one's own cultural identity.	Ager, A., & Strang, A. (2008). Understanding integration: A conceptual framework. <i>Journal of Refugee Studies</i> , 21 (2), 166–191.
2.2	Inclusion		Inclusion refers to the practice of ensuring that individuals from diverse backgrounds and abilities are actively integrated and valued within various social contexts. It is a fundamental concept in social and human sciences, emphasizing equitable access to opportunities and resources. Inclusion plays a vital role in shaping effective social policies that foster community cohesion and mutual respect. Within the framework of EGAL-I, we will primarily use the term 'inclusion' as it corresponds to the approach of the project.	UNESCO. (n.d.). Inclusion. Retrieved January 28, 2026, from https://www.unesco.org/en/query-list/inclusion
2.3.	Refugee inclusion in higher education		Inspired by Fisk et al. (2018) who called for "service inclusion" to counter exclusion practices imposed on people experiencing vulnerability we understand Refugee inclusion in higher education as fair access to, fair treatment during and fair opportunity to exit higher education for refugees.	Fisk, R., Dean, A. M., Alkire, L., Joubert, A., Preville, J., Robertson, N., & Rosenbaum, M. S. (2018). Design for service inclusion: Creating inclusive service systems by 2050. <i>Journal of Service Management</i> , 29 (5), 834–858.
3. Project objectives				

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3.1.	Socio-linguistic and academic inclusion		<p><i>Socio-linguistic</i> refers to “how language is used in different groups in society” (Cambridge English dictionary, n.d.). Within the context of higher education (HE), socio-linguistic inclusion denotes the capacity of a refugee student to engage fully in the social and academic life of the host country. This engagement occurs not only through the acquisition and practical use of the national language, but also through exposure to the social norms, practices, and values that underpin the host society.</p> <p><i>Academic</i> is a term referring to the social environment created within academic settings. This type of inclusion denotes the refugee student’s appropriation of the higher education (HE) norms, practices, and codes of the host country.</p>	<p>Cambridge University Press. (n.d.). <i>Academic</i>. In <i>Cambridge English dictionary</i>. Retrieved February 1, 2026, from https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/academic</p> <p>Cambridge University Press. (n.d.). <i>Socio</i>. In <i>Cambridge English dictionary</i>. Retrieved February 1, 2026, from https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/socio?q=socio-</p> <p>Cambridge University Press. (n.d.). <i>Sociolinguistic</i>. In <i>Cambridge English dictionary</i>. Retrieved February 1, 2026, from https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/sociolinguistic</p>
3.2.	Social Justice		<p>Social justice is understood as an underlying principle for peaceful and prosperous coexistence within and among nations. It represents the aspiration to a world in which societies are based on the principles of equality and solidarity, understand and value human rights, and recognize the dignity of every human being. The five key principles of social justice are often considered as including: the recognition that different people have different needs and circumstances (equity); ensuring that everyone has access to the resources and opportunities they need to succeed (access); enabling all individuals to play in role in the political, economic and social life of the communities (participation); protecting the human rights of all individuals (rights) and valuing and respecting differences between people, such as race, gender, and sexual orientation (diversity). In a 'socially just' context, individuals can develop and update the necessary capacities and skills they need to enable them to be productively occupied for their personal fulfilment and the common well-being; all enterprises, public or private, are sustainable to enable growth and the generation of greater employment and income opportunities and prospects for all; and societies can achieve their goals of economic development, good living standards and social progress.</p>	<p>United Nations. (2025, February 19). What is social justice and how is the UN helping make it a reality? https://news.un.org/en/story/2025/02/1160301</p> <p>International Labour Organization (2008). ILO declaration on social justice for a fair globalization. https://www.ilo.org/sites/default/files/2024-12/ILO-Declaration-2008_En.pdf</p>
3.3.	Open innovation & entrepreneurship		<p>Open innovation refers to the “opening up” of an organisations’ innovation process to the wider public. Rooted in the perception that no organisation has the “monopoly of great ideas” (European Commission, 2016.), open innovation requires the combination of internal organisational resources (e.g. company expertise) with external ones (e.g. local knowledge, capacities) to co-design and develop society-oriented and open solutions.</p> <p>Entrepreneurship is when you act upon opportunities and ideas and transform them into value for others. The value that is created can be financial, cultural, or social and can be shared within private, public or third sectors. Entrepreneurship is associated with specific competences, such as creativity, vision, taking the initiative and mobilising others.</p>	<p>European Commission. (2016, March 3). What is open innovation. Shaping Europe’s digital future. https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/what-open-innovation.</p> <p>Bacigalupo, M., Kampylis, P., Punie, Y., & Van den Brande, L. (2016). EntreComp: The entrepreneurship competence framework (EUR 27939 EN). Publications Office of the European Union. https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC101581</p>
4. Support Measures & Interventions				
4.1.	Actions	<i>Refugee study orientation programmes / Interventions / Transformative service initiatives (TSIs) / Informal support</i>	<p>Actions, that, in EGAL-I, is approached as an umbrella term, encompass a broad range of activities, measures, and initiatives aimed at fostering the inclusion, participation, and academic success of refugees and internally displaced persons in higher education. These actions may target educational, social, structural, or personal barriers and contribute to creating more equitable and supportive learning environments.</p>	Own definition
4.1.1.	Transformative Service Initiatives (TSIs)		<p>Transformative Service Initiatives (TSIs) are activities of organizations (public, private, nonprofit) or volunteers that serve people experiencing vulnerabilities and improve their well-being.</p>	Boenigk, S., Kreimer, A. A., Becker, A., Alkire, L., Fisk, R. P., & Kabadayi, S. (2021). Transformative service initiatives: enabling access and overcoming barriers for people experiencing vulnerability. <i>Journal of Service Research</i> , 24(4), 542-562.
4.1.2.	Informal support		<p>Informal support is typically understood as assistance available by nonprofessionals through one’s informal networks of e.g. family, friends, neighbourhood resources, faith based groups and in the EGAL-I use case other refugees.</p>	Boateng, G. O., Wachter, K., Schuster, R. C., Burgess, T. L., & Bunn, M. (2024). A scoping review of instruments used in measuring social support among refugees in resettlement. <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i> , 21(6), 805.
4.2.	Academic guidance / study support		<p>Any support or initiatives undertaken by higher education institutions and/or civil society to help refugee students start or continue their studies in the host country. This may include language learning programmes, academic upgrading, assistance with applying for bachelor’s, master’s or doctoral programmes, sociolinguistic and intercultural workshops, and tutoring or mentoring groups.</p>	Own definition

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4.3.	Psychosocial support		Psychosocial support for refugees is understood as a comprehensive set of actions and services aimed at restoring and strengthening refugees' mental health, social relationships, capacity to adapt to a new environment, and ability to cope with experienced trauma, including emotional and psychological support, social integration and community-building activities. As well as educational, employment, and housing support that contribute to the overall wellbeing of a person. It is highly emphasized that such support should be culturally sensitive and focused not only on medical interventions but also on community support, a sense of safety, and social inclusion in order to manage stress and isolation and promote wellbeing of refugees.	UNHCR. (2013). UNHCR's mental health and psychosocial support for persons of concern. https://www.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/legacy-pdf/51bec3359.pdf?utm_source=unhcr.org&utm_medium=pdf&utm_campaign=51bec3359.pdf UNHCR. (UNHCR) UNHCR. (2024). Mental health and psychosocial support. https://www.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/legacy-pdf/51bec3359.pdf?utm_source=unhcr.org&utm_medium=pdf&utm_campaign=51bec3359.pdf Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC). (2007). IASC guidelines on mental health and psychosocial support in emergency settings. https://interagencystandingcommittee.org/iasc-guidelines-mental-health-and-psychosocial-support-emergency-settings-2007 Nguyen, A. J., Lasater, M. E., Lee, C., Mallawaarachchi, I. V., Joshua, K., Bassett, L., & Geisdorf, K. (2023). Psychosocial support interventions in the context of forced displacement: A systematic review and meta-analysis. <i>Journal of migration and health</i> , 7, 100168. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmh.2023.100168
4.4.	Socio-linguistic support & Common European Framework of Reference for languages (CEFR)		This type of support includes language courses, digital and academic support workshops, mentoring programs, and other initiatives implemented within higher education institutions (HEIs) and the nonprofit and associative sectors. These measures aim to foster the inclusion of refugee students by supporting language learning, facilitating orientation within the education system and academic landscape, and promoting familiarity with HEI operations. These measures also address assessment practices and the academic written and oral genres that students are expected to produce in the host country. To identify language proficiency levels, reference is made to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages, including its extended version (CEFR; Council of Europe, 2001, 2020). However, CEFR levels and the associated certifications – often designed for foreign language learning contexts and frequently obtained abroad – tend to fall short of the actual needs of refugee students in second-language situations. In such contexts, the national language is not only learned but also used for studying, working and living in the host country. This category also includes HE staff and social actors from civil society who provide linguistic, social, and academic support to refugee students. The EGAL-I project aims to support these individuals by offering training focused on the academic requirements and expectations of HEIs.	Council of Europe. (2001). <i>Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, teaching, assessment</i> . Cambridge University Press. Council of Europe. (2020). <i>Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, teaching, assessment – Companion volume</i> . Council of Europe Publishing. https://www.coe.int/en/web/common-european-framework-reference-languages
4.5.	Social and tangible support		Social and logistic support refers to the services offered to students to support them during their studies. The different, specific types of social support that an individual may experience include emotional support (listening support, comfort, and security), informational support (advice and guidance), esteem support (increasing the person's sense of competence), and tangible support (concrete assistance such as providing transportation or financial assistance). Examples in HEIs are housing, financial assistance, and access to medical services. The availability and scope of these services depend on the organisation and autonomy of individual HEIs.	Drageset J. Social Support. 2021 Mar 12. In: Haugan G, Eriksson M, editors. <i>Health Promotion in Health Care – Vital Theories and Research</i> [Internet]. Cham (CH): Springer; 2021. Chapter 11. Available from: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK585650/ doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-63135-2_11
4.6.	Legal support	<i>Legal aid / Legal advice / Legal counselling / Legal assistance</i>	Legal support encompasses various forms of advice, services and information to help individuals or groups to understand legal matters and face legal proceedings. It can include the provision of basic information and material support to facilitate the handling of legal matters for a person or group in need. It can also entail the provision of assistance to people who are unable to afford legal representation and access to the court system. In this case, it foresees access to professional legal advice regarding the substance or procedure of the law in relation to a particular factual situation. The provision of legal advice involves analysing a set of facts and advising a person to take a specific course of action based on the applicable law. In many countries, people in need can access free legal aid which can cover representation in civil, criminal, and administrative cases. Pro bono services are also available for specific needs. Legal support is central for guaranteeing access to justice by ensuring equality before the law, the right to counsel and the right to a fair trial.	Wikipedia contributors. (2026, February 2). <i>Legal advice</i> . In Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. Retrieved February 18, 2026, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Legal_advice Refugee.info Italy. (2024, February 22). <i>Informations pour les personnes ayant demandé un permis de travail avec la sanatoria</i> . Refugee.info Italy. Retrieved February 18, 2026, from https://italy.refugee.info/articles/5388944842135
4.7.	Crowd-based innovation actions		Crowd-based innovation includes the active engagement and participation of a large group of individuals, usually through digital means, in the production or exchange of knowledge, goods and services for a social purpose. Crowd-based innovation actions are often self-organised, based on grassroots initiative, or promoted by official institutions. A concrete example of a crowd-based innovation action is hackathons. Hackathons are usually a 2 or 3-day competition (face-to-face, online or hybrid) where individuals work in teams to ideate, design and develop solutions (prototypes) that address socio-technological challenges.	Cuppen, E., Klievink, B., & Doorn, N. (2019). Governing crowd-based innovations: An interdisciplinary research agenda. <i>Journal of Responsible Innovation</i> , 6(2), 232–239. https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2019.1586511
5. Outcomes				
5.1.	Empowerment (socio-linguistic and academic)		Empowerment is defined as “the process of gaining freedom and power in order to do what you want or to control what happens to you” (Cambridge English Dictionary, n.d.). It is also understood as “a process through which women and men in disadvantaged positions increase their access to knowledge, resources and decision-making power, and enhance their participation within their communities, in order to achieve a degree of control over their own environment” (UNHCR, 2001, p. 3). The term of empowerment within this framework is not aimed solely at refugee students, but at all individuals, both within and outside HEIs, supporting them in their socio-linguistic and academic inclusion.	Cambridge University Press. (n.d.). <i>Empowerment</i> . In Cambridge English Dictionary. Retrieved February 1, 2026, from https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/empowerment United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. (2001). <i>A practical guide to empowerment</i> . UNHCR. https://www.unhcr.org/media/practical-guide-empowerment

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5.2.	Access to rights		The concept of access to rights entails that every person, especially those in more vulnerable and precarious situations, are entitled to enjoy full human rights and all other rights under national and international law. The concept also relates to the challenges that specific people and groups face in accessing these rights, for example because they are particularly affected by economic, social, geopolitical and environmental problems. Unemployment, precariousness, discrimination and social exclusion, for example, are barriers for many irregular migrant people in accessing their rights. Ensuring an even access to rights in a society is an essential element to establish a culture based on the principles of human rights, democracy and the rule of law. Promoting access to rights for every person means improving disadvantaged groups' access to rights and services through coordinated policy and civil society action; raising awareness of such rights; providing everyday support; offering legal protection; and performing advocacy actions.	<p>Council of Europe. (n.d.). <i>Access to rights</i>. Retrieved February 18, 2026, from https://www.coe.int/en/web/youth/access-to-rights</p> <p>Red Cross EU Office. (n.d.). <i>Improving migrants' access to rights and services through coordinated civil society action</i>. Retrieved February 18, 2026, from https://redcross.eu/projects/improving-migrants-access-to-rights-and-services-through-coordinated-civil-society-action</p>
5.3.	Development of entrepreneurship competences		Based on the European Commission's Entrepreneurship Competence Framework, there are 3 competence areas when it comes to entrepreneurship, namely: a) ideas and opportunities, b) resources, and c) into action. These include specific competences, such as: ethical and sustainable thinking, creativity, self-awareness, motivation, planning and management. Thus, the EGAL-I action with Ukrainian students will aim to enhance the development of such entrepreneurship skills to them.	Bacigalupo, M., Kampylis, P., Punie, Y., & Van den Brande, L. (2016). <i>EntreComp: The entrepreneurship competence framework</i> (EUR 27939 EN). Publications Office of the European Union. https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC101581
5.4.	Access to higher education		Access to higher education refers to the opportunity or ability of individuals to enter studies at a higher education institution. It involves formal (prior school qualifications, language certificate, admission rules etc.) and informal conditions (knowledge, social support etc.) that determine whether people can apply, enrol and enter higher education.	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2019). <i>Global convention on the recognition of qualifications concerning higher education. (UNESCO Convention)</i> . UNESCO. https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373602
5.5.	Participation in higher education		Participation in higher education refers to students actively making use of their access to higher education by engaging in the academic activities offered by the institution. This includes attending seminars and lectures, contributing to discussions, asking questions, presenting ideas, participating in collaborative learning and continuously progressing within one's study programme.	Own definition
5.6.	Sense of belonging	Social inclusion / Identification as student	Sense of belonging refers to an individual's subjective feeling of being accepted, valued, and connected to a social group or community he lives in. In migration and higher education contexts, it describes the extent to which migrants or international students feel included in the host society, country and/or academic community. Individuals experience this if he has meaningful relationships with people and feel overall psychological wellbeing, which is crucial for successful integration and academic adjustment.	<p>Dias-Broens, A. S. (2024). The definition and measurement of sense of belonging in higher education: A systematic review. <i>Educational Research Review</i>.</p> <p>Froehlich, L., Brokjob, L. G., Nikitin, J., & Martiny, S. E. (2023). Integration or isolation: Social identity threat relates to immigrant students' sense of belonging and social approach motivation in the academic context. <i>Journal of Social Issues</i>, 79(1), 264-290.</p>
5.7.	Completion of studies		Refers to the successful completion of the academic program that a student has started. It means that all required coursework and examinations have been fulfilled and the study program is formally finished. In most cases, this is associated with receiving an academic degree such as a Bachelor's or Master's.	Own definition
5.8.	Resilience		Resilience can be defined as an individual's or an institution's ability to withstand a brutal ordeal, a traumatic circumstance, and live satisfactorily or even transform it to become stronger. In the context of a higher education institution, this can translate into the institution's ability to recover after an external disruption. In the case of our project, we will focus on both the resilience of refugee students and the resilience of higher education institutions and citizen communities. With refugee students, we will focus on how our actions contribute to supporting their inclusion towards resilience. With higher education institutions and citizen communities, we will focus on their capacity to cope with a significant influx of refugee students and create positive externalities from this experience. We are adopting the European Commission's approach on resilience which is linked to crisis management. It means "bringing [actors] together, in an integrated way, the different socio-economic sectors and systems to address all phases of risk management: from prevention and preparedness to response and recovery".	<p>Joint Research Centre. (n.d.). <i>Risks and resilience</i>. European Commission – JRC Science for a resilient EU. Retrieved February 18, 2026, from https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/scientific-portfolios/risks-and-resilience_en</p> <p>Ministère de la Culture. (n.d.). <i>Résilience</i> (terme AFET20). In <i>FranceTerme</i>. Retrieved February 18, 2026, from https://www.culture.fr/franceterme/terme/AFET20</p>